

THERMOPLASTIC BRAID PULTRUSION

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SUMMARY

At ITV Denkendorf, a pulbraiding equipment was installed to enhance torsional stability of thin walled rectangular profiles. Twintex hybrid yarns and tubular profiles with thermoset matrix were produced. Optimized process- and fibre handling parameters resulted in profiles with up to 25°-braiding angle with high surface quality, good consolidation and uniform dimensions. Further research work is carried out on realising hollow tubular profiles with enhanced bending stiffness and damping properties using biomimetic approaches. Also thermoplastic matrix systems allow to reshape the cross section and the curving radius.

Keywords: thermoplastic, pulbraiding, biomimetics, post forming

THERMOPLASTIC PULTRUSION

To extent the use of pultrusion technique, pultrusion processes with enhanced functionality are in advance, e.g. bigger parts with more cores (PHOENIX, USA), 3-dimensional curved parts (JAMCO, Japan; FIBRE INNOVATIONS, USA), or changing the geometry during the process (PULTRUSION DYNAMICS, USA). For higher torsional stiffness/tenacity additionally woven fabrics, spiralized fibres (pulwinding, Exel, Finland) or braided fibres (pulbraiding, PRINCE, Netherlands; SECAR, Austria, BERGAL, Germany) are incorporated. The advantage of pulbraiding is the mutual supporting of the fibres in the braided structure. This causes less fibre disorientation when the fibres are pulled into the die. Fig. 1 shows two profiles with different braiding angles resulting in different mechanical properties.

Fig. 1: Different braiding angles

The possibility of changing the braiding angle during the process in braid-pultrusion enables the production of gradient profiles where the fibres are aligned much better to match the forces. The advantages of thermoplastic matrix also brought forward the pultrusion of reinforced thermoplastics. Impregnation of thermoset pultrusion is made by a bath or injection, high viscous thermoplastics are “impregnated” by powder, injection of melted polymer, low viscous polymer solution, pre-polymers (in situ polymerization) or with the use of comingled hybrid yarns, e.g. Twintex-hybrid-yarn (OCV) or ITV air-commingled hybrid yarns. During pultrusion, impregnated yarns or textiles are pre-heated and pulled through the die. In the tapered feeding zone the melting matrix impregnates and encases the reinforcing fibres, in the following consolidation zone the impregnated fibres are compacted to ensure a void free matrix and full impregnation.

ITV-BRAID-PULTRUSION

With ITV-braid-pultrusion (Fig. 2) fundamental work on the production of thin walled hollow profiles was made with hybrid yarns (e.g. Twintex™). This equipment works with a fixed steel core. After defining and optimizing influencing factors, profiles with adjustable and sufficient mechanical properties and smooth surfaces could be produced (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2: ITV-Braid-Pultrusion-machinery

Fig. 3: Thermoplastic-Braid Pultrusion

BIONIC-BRAID-PULTRUSION

Another Braid-Pultrusion Project deals with the bionic transfer of plant biomechanics into technique. Research work of the plant biomechanics group of University Freiburg shows that horsetail (Fig 4) and giant reed have very high specific mechanical properties combined with high oscillation damping of strong wind-induced vibration. This structure was transferred into technique by braid pultrusion technology (Fig. 5)

Fig 4: Horsetail

Fig. 5: Technical plant stem

POST-FORMING

The use of a thermoplastic matrix allows post forming of pultruded profiles. Thus better consolidated composites can be produced or the profiles can be transformed into other shapes or radii. If a already curved profile is produced, post forming the profile in a press will result in a profile with different radii. The braiding helps to belt the structure.

Fig. 6: Production of curved profiles at ITV Denkendorf

The use of thermoplastic matrix system gives the possibility to create a faster and better connection of a tube to a hub. In contrast to a riveted shaft-hub joint (Fig. 7), a heated tube can be post formed onto a corrugated hub establishing both a form and a force closure between tube and hub. Again, the braided fibres belt the structure and hinder the fibres to unlock. If a technical plant stem is used as a tubular material (Fig. 8), the possible glued surface area is even bigger than a single wall tube. If the hub is machined

in a special way with pins to connect to the whole surface area, there will be a substantial enhanced connection between rod and hub.

Fig 7: Riveted shaft-hub joint
(Source: Xperion)

Fig. 8: Enhanced glued surface of the
technical plant stem

APPLICATIONS

The applications for thermoplastic matrix composites are manifold. More and more composite parts are produced with thermoplastic matrix systems, because of advantages in production speed, recycling possibilities, fatigue endurance limits, weldability and toughness. The possibility to post form the profiles will lead to new application areas, for example in the aerospace, where the amount of pieces in a lot rises steadily. For example, in near future there will be a demand for 500.000 composite window frames per year for airbus aircrafts, and a large number of straight and curved stiffeners and stringers (Fig 9).

Fig. 9: Stiffeners and stringers, curved & straight
(Source: Boeing)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research work was funded by the ministry of science, research and arts of Baden Württemberg and the German federal ministry of education and research.